

On the Development of European Design Rules for Re-Used Steel Components

Helen Bartsch^{*,a}, Felix Eyben^a, Markus Feldmann

^aInstitute of Steel Construction, RWTH Aachen University, Germany
h.bartsch@stb.rwth-aachen.de; f.eyben@stb.rwth-aachen.de; feldmann@stb.rwth-aachen.de

ABSTRACT

In the construction sector, the direct Re-Use of components holds promise as a significant contributor to enhanced sustainability and resource conservation. Re-using components is particularly applicable to steel structures due to their high level of pre-fabrication and the ease and speed of construction and dismantling processes. Nevertheless, the utilization of re-used steel components in structural applications requires the establishment of concepts and guidelines for survey, reclaiming, stockage, placing on the market, design and installation.

To facilitate widespread steel component Re-use in construction across European countries, it is essential to define rules for the safety assessments and designs for re-used steel components. This paper outlines crucial aspects essential for a secure EC3 design of re-used steel members, proposing possible approaches for a new technical specification. The discussion encompasses the current state of research and standardisation regarding Re-Use. For the development of a technical specification addressing the design rules for re-used components, a comprehensive examination of the process chain is necessary. The paper scrutinizes various steps in the process chain, with a primary focus on the "Component Assessment and Classification" stage. Existing assessment methods are presented and an example on assessing fundamental variables is offered, along with potential updating procedures.

It is evident that the formulation of design rules for re-used steel components will be essential in determining the trajectory of sustainable steel construction in the future.

Keywords: Sustainability, Re-Use, Design

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General

In order to combat the climate crisis, the Inter-Governmental Panel on Climate Change had proposed a target of reducing global emissions by a minimum of 50% by 2050, relative to the levels observed in 2000. Notably, the steel and aluminium industries play significant roles in global emissions, contributing to 10% of anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions from energy and industrial processes [1]. An examination of potential efficiency enhancements revealed that solely improving production efficiency and maximizing recycling rates, even at an ambitious 90% for both metals, cannot alone achieve the reduction of global emissions. This limitation stems from the fact that the primary energy-intensive processes in these industries are already operating at high levels of efficiency, even several years ago [2].

Since that time, there has been no amelioration in the prevailing circumstances, still necessitating the development of novel strategies and solutions.

Here, the non-destructive direct Re-Use of components holds great potential efficiency, as it circumvents the elevated energy expenses associated with recycling through melting. This is achieved by preserving the microstructure and geometry of the existing components, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Re-Use in the process of steel life cycle (green arrows)

However, the structural or load-bearing steel components intended for Re-Use generally do not meet the necessary requirements according to EN 1090-1 (conformity) [3] and EN 1090-2 (execution) [4], in particular it can be assumed that the proof of usability is generally missing. There is a lack of standardized requirements for the load-bearing capacity and serviceability of dismantled structural components or structural parts made of steel that are intended for Re-Use in structures without or with the necessary refurbishment.

Regulations of the different parts of EN 1993 [5] have been developed for “new” or “fresh” components, excluding components that had been incorporated in a first structural context and are demolished and installed in a second structural context.

There are initial ideas for the development of suitable standards on the topic “Design of re-used Steel Construction Components” in line with EN 1993 [5], see also [6, 7, 8, 9], which are described in this paper.

1.2 Clarification of Terms and Context

When discussing the direct Re-Use of steel structural components, it is important to distinguish this practice from recycling and the assessment of existing structures, including retrofitting efforts, see Fig. 2:

- 1. Material Recycling:** In the process of recycling steel components, the structural context is completely eliminated, and there is no preservation of the component's original form. Instead, a “rebirth” of the building material occurs through melting in an electric arc furnace.

2. **Assessment and Retrofitting of Structures:** This term involves the preservation of the structural framework, encompassing repair and strengthening within the same structural context and under the same boundary conditions, potentially undergoing different loading scenarios.
3. **Re-Use of Components including Design:** In this context, the utilization of dismantled components is executed within a different structural framework, different boundary conditions and subjected to different loading scenarios as before.

Fig. 2 Differentiation between Re-Use, recycling and retrofitting

The **Definition of a re-used component** can be stated as follows [9]:

“Component, removed from an existing structure and reinstalled in another structural context, as a whole or in parts, possibly with modifications, extensions, or strengthening. A re-used steel component does not need to be “old”. It can be of any age.” [9]

The **Design of re-used components** needs to be understood in two respects:

1. Firstly, as a task for the design of new components and structures being particularly suited for Re-Use of components in future – **“Design for Re-Use of Components”** –, as well as
2. Secondly, as a task for design of new structures using used components – **“Design of Re-used Components”**. The latter is the focus of the investigations described in this paper.

Presently, the focus lies predominantly on the treatment of components pertaining to building structures. Subsequently, bridges and other engineering structures may be considered. It is important to note that the current context does not encompass design regulations for instances where re-used components are subjected to fatigue or seismic loading, whether in the past or future.

2 STATE-OF-THE-ART REGARDING RESEARCH AND STANDARDISATION

2.1 Research

Re-Use topics have become increasingly important in the field of research, especially in the last 5 years. However, the first **general studies** also date back to the 2000s. Geyer at al. performed first economic and environmental comparisons between recycling and Re-Use of structural steel sections. The study shows that there are strong environmental and economic arguments in favor of a shift from the recycling of steel profiles to their Re-Use. However, the potential of Re-Use is limited by the fact that there are bottlenecks in the profile Re-Use cycle, such as limited dismantling, limited technical feasibility or limited market demand [10]. There were also initial proposals for a Re-Use overall business system at the time [11]. Cooper's work assesses the worldwide opportunities for Re-Use of steel and aluminium components by analysing global production and categorizing key characteristics such as design specifications, usage requirements and Re-Use patterns of that time [12, 13] He also reviewed the potential benefits and pitfalls of Re-Use [14]. In the UK, Re-Use has been a major issue for a while. Here, for example, surveys of British demolition companies were carried out to estimate the Re-Use and recycling rates of steel construction products from the demolition of buildings in the UK. In 2012, 5% of the steel used was re-used [15].

Numerous **case studies** on Re-Use were also carried out, e.g. to quantify the savings that can be achieved through Re-Use in Italy [16], to evaluate the performance of the Re-Use of steel structural members for plants, warehouses and offices [17] and gable frames [18] or to compare cost and environmental burdens of Re-Use in the life-cycle study of a selected girder [19]. Re-Use is also an important research topic in Finland, so that case studies were also carried out here, for example on a method for predicting the reusability of building components and whole structures in terms of a pilot study of three different single-storey steel buildings [20].

Many studies have also described the **barriers** that have so far stood in the way of the Re-Use of steel, e.g. [21] describing the UK perspective, [22] giving insights into the Belgian construction sector and [23] summarising input from several countries as Canada, Germany, Japan, Netherlands, etc.

Another research area from the Re-Use field is **design for Re-Use**. Here, for example, easily demountable connections, like a block shear connector [24], or material banks and a design support tools [25] are being investigated and established.

Recent research studies on Re-Use refer to **innovative technologies**: Here, for example, it was investigated whether Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology coupled with Building Information Modeling (BIM) may enable components to be tracked and imported into virtual models for new buildings during the design stage [26]. Also, semi-automated geometry characterisation techniques are developed in order to simplify Re-Use processes [27].

A more widespread approach to promoting Re-Use is the demonstration of sustainability by means of **life cycle assessments** (LCA), see e.g. [28]. The authors suggested a methodology for assessing the ecological impact of multi-use steel halls, based on LCA, by employing a cumulative approach to ecological, economic, and technical parameters and utilizing a generalized ecological indicator for a practical evaluation.

It becomes progressively evident that extensive research is being conducted in diverse domains related to Re-Use. Furthermore, initial normative guidelines have already been established, as briefly elaborated in the subsequent section.

2.2 Normative Regulations

The issue of Re-Use is addressed in some existing standards, such as the American standard ANSI/AISC 360-16 [29]. This standard primarily focuses pipe supports and scaffolding, less on the

Re-Use of structural steel components. Annex 5 of [29] provides a **test procedure** for determining material properties of old steel at specified locations through destructive tests, such as tensile tests. Furthermore, regulations on the **execution** in the context of Re-Use is worked on: In the draft version of prEN 1090-x [30], rules for dismantling steel structures and testing methods based on the available information about the structure to be re-used are specified. Additionally, the British Constructional Steelwork Association has formulated rules [31] for the sale and purchase of re-used steel profiles, including regulations on tolerance handling. Further sustainable requirements for steel structures are outlined in [32].

Product standards, such as prEN 17662 [33], also exhibit changes and developments where Re-Use options are increasingly incorporated. Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) contribute to the trend of considering a steel structure or component within its entire life cycle.

In addition to standards, numerous **guidelines** on Re-Use exist. In Switzerland, the Steel Construction Centre published a guide [34] focusing on the Re-Use of steel components, with an emphasis on structural analysis, quality management, and surface protection. Furthermore, a guideline [35] by the Steel Construction Institute provides design principles for different load cases and general rules on the Re-Use of steel components. The discussion of CE-marking according to EN 1090-2 [4] is also included in this guideline.

However, **design standards** for re-used components are still missing. For the development of a technical specification addressing the design rules for re-used components, a comprehensive examination of the process chain is necessary, as outlined in the following.

3 PROCESS CHAIN FOR THE RE-USE OF STEEL COMPONENTS

Fig. 3 Process Chain Steps for the Re-Use of Steel Components, see also [9]

In its entirety, the subject of "Component Re-Use" extends beyond mere design considerations. Instead, it necessitates the establishment of an entire Process Chain. Initially, it is crucial to emphasize that both industry and authorities should work towards creating a system that facilitates the Process Chain for construction with re-used structural steel components. From a design standpoint, it is crucial to verify that the re-used components possess the essential properties aligning with the assumptions made during the design phase. The safety evaluation and corresponding classification of the components must be adjusted accordingly.

Fig. 3 outlines a proposed Process Chain for the Re-Use of structural steel components, encompassing eight sequential steps (PC Steps) from Deconstruction (PC Step 1) to Installation (Step 8).

In view of Design regulations, especially Step 2, Step 3 and Step 6 are of importance, which will be outlined in the following sections.

3.1 Component Survey: Inspection and Testing

When surveying components by inspection and testing, the degree of examination should depend on the age of the construction, the function of the component in the structure and the kind and extent of the preliminary information.

Special attention must be given to the treatment of welds. In the past, specifications for workmanship quality, such as EN ISO 5817 [36], were not as detailed as today. Consequently, it is anticipated that re-used components may have a higher occurrence of welding defects compared to new components. However, it is noteworthy that welds that do not adhere to the quality standards of EN ISO 5817 (linked with execution classes EXC 1, 2, or 3 of EN 1090-2 [4]) often demonstrate sufficient strength, see [37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42]. An assessment pathway is being explored to appropriately categorize "old" welds within the EXC framework.

In general, standardized inspection and testing protocols and procedures must be defined for an inclusion into normative regulations.

3.2 Component Assessment of Design Properties and Classification

The component assessment depicts the basis for the resistance to be assumed in the design. Background for the assessment depicts the data of inspection and testing. Essentially, the evaluation should follow the guidelines of CEN/TS 17440 [43] and EN 1990-2 [44], respectively. This allows for the classification of the component based on "design classes."

In a general sense, component assessment involves the assessment of basic variables. Prior to introducing a re-used structural component to the market for installation in a new structure, it is necessary to evaluate its properties and resistances in relation to the limit states for the design process. Given that the guidelines in [43] are designed for the assessment of existing structures,

specific details regarding the Re-Use of existing components for installation in new structures may vary.

CEN/TS 17440 [43] outlines procedures for "updating" of basic variables in both the main text and Annex B of the document. The informative Annex details procedures for:

- Updating probability distributions, mean values, characteristic values, or assessment values of fundamental variables.
- Updating the probability of structural failure through the incorporation of testing results or information regarding past performance [43].

Fig. 4 Example for Updating Procedures [9]

direct influence on the value of the partial safety factor γ_M of the design. In this context, we assume that material certificates for components of a steel construction under consideration as an example provide knowledge about material properties (prior information, represented by the brown curve).

Additional material samples are then collected (sample, depicted by the blue curve). In this scenario, an updating procedure in accordance with [43] can be executed, resulting in posterior information (represented by the grey curve). This curve reflects the "updated" material characteristics derived from both prior and sampled information.

It's worth noting that when dealing with re-used steel components, certain distinctive aspects arise, mainly from the process downstream. Therefore, relying solely on an updating procedure is not adequate for a thorough assessment; more intricate sub-steps are necessary, as explained in detail in reference [9].

Furthermore, it's important to ascertain the compatibility of old steels or steel products with the rules in EN 1993 [5]. For this, a specific examination called "CovEx-Investigation" is recommended, as described in the following section.

3.3 PC Step 6 "Design"

Structural steel components that are re-used undergo essentially the same design procedure as new structural steel components, including modifications. The safety elements and characteristic values, however, may vary based on the production and condition of the component.

When designing a structure using re-used components, the same verification process is required as for structures with new components. It must be ensured that no limit state is exceeded in any applicable design situation. The design process should be conducted using the partial factor method. The effects of actions and resistance values can be represented as functions of the assessment values of basic variables. This includes the relevant partial factors, combination factors, and conversion factors, adjusted for re-used components.

From a design perspective, the initial consideration for re-used components involves assessing how they can be verified for structural safety and which standards apply. To facilitate this assessment, the following differentiation might prove useful [9]:

Tab. 1 Prioritised CovEx Cases [9]

CovEx Case 1	Components to be re-used, design fully covered by EN 1993	Priority 1
CovEx Case 2	Components to be re-used, design covered by EN 1993, but with modifications	Priority 1
NonCovEx Case 1	Components to be re-used, design not covered by EN 1993, but background for additional rules available	Priority 2
NonCovEx Case 2	Components to be re-used, design not covered by EN 1993, background for additional rules to be researched	Priority 3

Safety provision for the design should then be based on the following three bases:

1. CovEx Case
2. Level of technical information on component and
3. Production period of component

Specifics still require further examination and clarification.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Re-Use of structural steel components holds the potential to make a substantial contribution towards decreasing carbon emissions in the construction sector. To enable this aim, a clear process chain and reliable design rules for re-used components, along with guidelines for execution and legal aspects are needed. In summary, the main ideas for creating European design rules for re-used steel components, as discussed in this paper, are the following:

1. The foundation of a new technical specification is rooted in a comprehensive review of existing research, which has been summarised in brief.
2. Several topics related to the main tasks for developing rules for re-used steel components have been identified and described, generally following the principles outlined in EN 1990-2 [44] or CEN/TS 17440 [43].
3. Moreover, a crucial aspect is to consider the applicability of existing rules from EN 1993 [3] and whether modifications are necessary for construction components or their parts from earlier periods. In this context, potential approaches for addressing these considerations have been presented.

5 OUTLOOK

The paper presents initial concepts for tackling the challenge of Re-Use from a design standpoint. However, specific approaches are yet to be thoroughly researched and defined in future investigations. The ultimate objective is to establish a detailed technical specification for the “Design of reclaimed steel components for Re-Use”. Developing design guidelines for the Re-Use of steel components will play a crucial role in shaping the future direction of sustainable steel construction.

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